

Boosted hyperthermia therapy by combined AC magnetic and photo-thermal exposures in Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers

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ABSTRACT

Over the past two decades magnetic hyperthermia and photo-thermal therapy are becoming very promising supplementary techniques to well-established cancer treatments such as radiotherapy and chemotherapy. These techniques have dramatically improved their ability to perform controlled treatments, relying on the procedure of delivering nanoscale objects into targeted tumor tissues, which can release therapeutic killing doses of heat either upon AC magnetic field exposure or laser irradiation. While an intense research effort has been made in recent years to study, separately, magnetic hyperthermia using iron oxide nanoparticles and photo-thermal therapy based on gold or silver plasmonic nanostructures, the full potential of combining both techniques has not yet been systematically explored. Here we present a proof-of-principle experiment showing that designing multifunctional silver/magnetite (Ag/Fe₃O₄) nanoflowers acting as dual hyperthermia agents is an efficient route for enhancing their heating ability or specific absorption rate (SAR). Interestingly, the SAR of the nanoflowers is increased by at least one order of magnitude under the application of both an external magnetic field of 200 Oe and simultaneous laser irradiation. Furthermore, our results show that the synergistic exploitation of the magnetic and photo-thermal properties of the nanoflowers reduces the magnetic field and laser intensities that would be required in case that both external stimuli were applied separately. This constitutes a key step towards optimizing the hyperthermia therapy through a combined multifunctional magnetic and photo-thermal treatment and improving our understanding of therapeutic process to specific applications that will entail coordinated efforts in physics, engineering, biology and medicine.

Keywords: Bifunctional nanoparticles; Nanoflowers, Magneto-thermal effect; Photo-thermal effect; Hyperthermia

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Equal contribution to the work.

INTRODUCTION

The use of nanotechnology for biomedical applications (nanobiotechnology), including among others cancer treatment, has generated a lot of expectations in the last two decades.¹⁻⁴ Despite the excellent research progress achieved, especially in the last few years, there is still much work to do in order to overcome the limitations that prevent nanobiotechnology methods from becoming a clinical reality. Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) are one of the best candidates for biomedical applications, due to optimal characteristics such as: ⁵⁻⁸ a controllable size that allows them to interact with cells, bacteria, viruses, etc.; the capability to respond and be controlled by an external magnetic field; a long blood circulation time when appropriately coated; the possibility of offering multifunctional response; etc. Specifically, MNP-based multifunctional hybrid nanostructures^{5,9-11} are expected to open up the path for the development of new biomedical tools for simultaneous imaging, diagnosis and therapeutics. Different strategies have been proposed in order to create nanostructures capable of providing complementary functionalities.^{9,10} For example, Nasongkla *et al.*¹² have demonstrated that polymeric micelles loaded with iron oxide MNPs and doxorubicin can be used both for controlled drug delivery and efficient magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast. On the other hand, Xu *et al.*¹³ have shown that dumbbell-shaped Au/Fe₃O₄ NPs are magnetically and optically active and therefore useful for cell imaging and detection.

In particular, hybrid core/shell or composite nanostructures made from the combination of plasmonic metals and magnetic iron oxide have gained considerable attention from the scientific community owing to their prospective multifunctional properties ranging from imaging and diagnosis to therapeutics.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ The metallic component of these multifunctional hybrid nanostructures can be used for the imaging and diagnostics thanks to the strong localized plasmon resonant optical response, whereas the magnetic component can provide additional contrast for MRI, targeted delivery, thermal heating, etc.

In the case of cancer treatment, one of the major public health concerns in our modern society,¹⁷ there is an emerging need for new approaches that assist in rapidly advancing diagnosis and treatment and can complement existing therapies based on chemotherapy and radiotherapy. To this respect, certain nanostructures used in localized hyperthermia have emerged as very promising agents for cancer treatment.¹⁸⁻²² By delivering the nanostructures to the tumor area and applying an external stimulus, the nanostructures can heat up and destroy the cancer cells without damaging the healthy ones, thus minimizing the collateral damage caused by other well established therapies. The two main non-invasive ways to treat cancer with heat originated from nanostructures are AC magnetic hyperthermia and photo-thermal therapy. In the first case, the external stimulus is an AC magnetic field, while electromagnetic radiation (most often using wavelengths within the infrared range) is commonly employed in the second case.

MNPs have been extensively studied for magnetic hyperthermia in the last few years.¹⁸ The heating effects of MNPs under an AC magnetic field can be due to diverse energy loss processes (hysteresis losses, Néel and Brown relaxation, etc.).^{23,24} Despite attaining some remarkable progress, the number of clinical trials is still very limited. One of the main limitations of using MNPs lies in the relatively small heating ability or low specific absorption rate (SAR) of the MNPs. Hergt *et al.*²⁵ have pointed out that, in order to optimize the current hyperthermia treatments and avoid using risky high concentrations of MNPs, their SAR values must be greatly enhanced. With the aim of improving the heating efficiency of MNPs, researchers have employed different strategies such as exchange coupled magnets, effective anisotropy enhancement and others.²⁶⁻³⁰ For photo-thermal therapy, gold and silver NPs are most commonly used due to their strong plasmonic properties.³¹⁻³³ When illuminating these NPs with light of an appropriate wavelength, a coherent excitation of surface electrons is induced, followed by a rapid relaxation that generates local heat.³⁴⁻³⁶ While there was some concern about the effective light penetration in the human tissue,³⁷ recent studies have revealed that NIR light travels at least 10 cm through breast tissue, and 4 cm of skull/brain tissue or deep muscle using microwatt laser sources (Food and Drug

Administration (FDA) class 1. With higher power levels (FDA class 3), the light has been shown to penetrate through 7 cm of muscle and neonatal skull/brain.³⁸ This was further verified by Henderson *et al.*³⁹ These studies indicate the possible use of photo-thermal heating for real life applications. In addition, gold and silver are not FDA approved materials. Nevertheless, coating gold and silver with a biocompatible material such as iron oxide could substantially mitigate this problem. In addition, coating with iron oxide enables a remote control of the nanoparticles with an external magnetic field, especially interesting in biomedicine.

Even though much research effort has been made to study, separately, AC hyperthermia using different types of iron oxide NPs and photo-thermal therapy based on plasmonic nanostructures, works covering both aspects are still rather scarce.⁴⁰⁻⁴¹ This restricts the promising possibility of designing multifunctional hybrid nanostructures with plasmonic and magnetic properties for simultaneous photo-thermal and AC magnetic hyperthermia.⁴² To address this challenge, we have fabricated nanocomposites constituted by clusters of Fe₃O₄ (magnetite) MNPs arranged like the petals of a flower around a silver core (hereafter called “nanoflower” structure).⁴³ Here we demonstrate that our Ag(core)/Fe₃O₄(shell) nanoflowers exhibit an improvement in heating efficiency by acting as dual agents for both photo-thermal therapy (Ag) and magnetic hyperthermia (Fe₃O₄).

METHODS

Ag(core)/Fe₃O₄(shell) nanoflowers were prepared using a one-step solvothermal process.⁴³ In a typical reaction, 1.16 g of iron nitrate nonahydrate [Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O] was dissolved in 35 ml of ethylene glycol, followed by the addition of 2.9 g of sodium acetate (NaAc) and 0.1 g of silver nitrate (AgNO₃). The solution was stirred for 30 minutes to dissolve all the reactants and then transferred to a 45 ml Teflon lined autoclave, where it was heated at 200° C for 24 h. After cooling the autoclave to room temperature, the obtained black precipitate was washed several times with water and ethanol. The final product was dispersed in ethanol for further characterization. The relative sizes of the core and the shell can be tailored by changing the concentration of the precursors during the synthesis process.

High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images, selected-area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopic images and line profiles were obtained using a JEOL-JEM-2100F microscope operating at 200 kV. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected using a Bruker AXS D8 X-ray diffractometer with Cu K_{α1} radiation (1.5406 Å). The absorption spectrum of the nanoflowers was recorded in the UV-Vis region using a Perkin Elmer Lambda 950 spectrophotometer.

DC magnetic measurements were performed using a physical property measurement system (PPMS-9T) by Quantum Design, with a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) option. The $M(T)$ curves were recorded under an applied field (H) of 100 Oe, following the zero-field-cooling and field-cooling (ZFC-FC) protocols, while the $M(H)$ loops were measured at room and low temperatures in magnetic field values up to 50 kOe.

Magnetic hyperthermia experiments were carried out by calorimetric method using a 4.2-kW Ambrell Easyheat Li3542 equipment under different AC magnetic field values ($H_{AC} = 0-800$ Oe) at a constant frequency ($f = 310$ kHz). The photo-thermal heating efficiency of the nanoflowers was investigated using laser radiation with wavelength of 442 nm and power densities (P) ranging from 0.13 to 1.60 W/cm². All magnetic hyperthermia and photo-thermal measurements were performed on agar (2 wt.% in water) dispersions with a constant concentration of Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers of 2 mg/ml. In addition, a nanoflower-free agar sample was measured under identical experimental conditions as a reference signal, its heating power being subtracted in the calculation of the SAR of the nanoflowers.

In addition to the calorimetric measurements, we have also recorded the AC hysteresis loops during magnetic hyperthermia experiments, using a home-made device⁴⁴ that is able to apply AC magnetic fields up to 400 Oe at a

frequency of 300 kHz. These provide us with a better depiction of the MNPs heating efficiency, as the SAR is directly proportional to the area of the hysteresis loop.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural characterization

HRTEM micrographs (Fig. 1a) reveal that our Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers have a relatively narrow size distribution, with a mean diameter (D) and a standard deviation (σ) of 120(10) nm, as deduced from the fit of the size histogram to a lognormal distribution (Figure S1 in the supplementary information). In the SAED pattern displayed in Fig. 1b, diffraction rings corresponding to two different phases are identified. While magnetite is detected in its typical spinel cubic crystal structure (space group $Fd-3m$; #227) with a cell parameter of $a_{\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4} = 8.39(1)$ Å, silver presents its characteristic face-centered-cubic phase (space group; $Fm-3m$; #225) with $a_{\text{Ag}} = 4.09(1)$ Å. It is worth noting that only Bragg reflections corresponding to these two crystal structures are observed in the XRD pattern (Figure S2 in the supplementary information). EDX elemental maps (see Fig. 1c and Figure S3 in the supplementary information) unambiguously confirm that Ag is localized inside the core of the nanoflowers and surrounded by an Fe₃O₄ shell. No evidence of interatomic diffusion between the Ag and the Fe₃O₄ is observed within the experimental resolution. Furthermore, the element-specific line profiles traced across a single nanoflower (Fig. 1d) provide an accurate determination of the core and shell dimensions. As a matter of fact, each core consists of a highly crystalline Ag monodomain of 45(10) nm (see Figs. 1e,f and Figure S4 in the supplementary information). By contrast, the shell has a nearly constant thickness of ~ 40 nm and is composed of aggregated and randomly oriented Fe₃O₄ nanocrystallites with an average size of 22(6) nm (Fig. 1g). The epitaxial growth of the Fe₃O₄ “petals” on top of the Ag monodomain leads to a smooth core/shell interface (Fig. 1f).

Absorption properties

In order to understand the subsequent photo-thermal properties of the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers, the absorption spectrum was examined. Two absorption bands are clearly observed and centered at ~ 400 nm and ~ 615 nm, respectively (Figure S5 in the supplementary information). Consistent with previous reports,⁴¹ the first band corresponds to the plasmon resonance of silver, while the second band is attributed to electronic transition processes in magnetite.⁴⁵ Therefore, we have used a laser in the visible violet spectrum (e.g. 442 nm laser radiation) for the photo-thermal experiments for a proof-of-concept demonstration purpose, as light of this frequency can cause substantial damage to tissue and cells. For clinical use, however, an absorption wavelength near the infrared range is preferable due to a deeper penetration capability into the human tissue.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹ This limitation can be overcome in our case by, for example, tuning the size, shape, and/or morphology of the Ag nanoparticles in order to displace the absorption window towards higher wavelength, as already reported in the literature.⁵⁰ For examples, Link *et al.* demonstrated an increase in the maximum absorption wavelength of Au nanoparticles with increasing particle size.⁵¹ Tao *et al.* reported that Ag nanocubes, cuboctahedra, and octahedra displayed very distinct scattering signatures despite possessing the same point group symmetry.⁵² Ying *et al.* also showed that by increasing the aspect ratio of Au nanorods, the absorption peaks could be displaced towards higher.⁵³ This is beyond the scope of the current manuscript and will be a subject for further systematic research in the future.

Magnetic characterization

The temperature and DC applied magnetic field dependences of the magnetization have been investigated before studying the hyperthermia response of the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers (Fig. 2). As depicted in Fig. 2a, the ZFC magnetization increases continuously on heating from low temperature. The absence of any overlapping in the ZFC and FC magnetization vs. T

curves in the whole temperature range of the measurements (up to $T = 328$ K) indicates that NPs are magnetically blocked; then, we can assume a blocked state for the NPs during our hyperthermia experiments. The well-defined shoulder observed around $T_V \sim 105$ K is the signature for the characteristic Verwey transition of magnetite.⁵⁴ At $T = T_V$, a change between the high-symmetry cubic (for $T > T_V$) and the low-symmetry monoclinic (for $T < T_V$) crystal structures occurs in Fe_3O_4 . Although T_V is well-defined in bulk materials, it is often not observable in small MNPs (< 10 nm),⁵⁵ this being associated with poor MNP crystallinity and a proliferation of surface defects.⁵⁶ The sharp Verwey transition observed in our Fe_3O_4 MNPs is a clear-cut indicator of their high degree of crystallinity. This is also supported by the remarkable value for the saturation magnetization ($M_S = 56$ emu/g) obtained from the room temperature $M(H)$ hysteresis loop (Figs. 2b,c). Taking into account the relative dimensions of the core and the shell we estimate a value of $M_S \sim 62$ emu/g for the magnetite NPs, which is almost 2/3 of the value corresponding to that of bulk magnetite, about 90 emu/g.⁵⁷ A high M_S value is especially important for magnetic hyperthermia, as it enhances the heating efficiency of the MNPs and improves their magnetic response under an external magnetic field during clinical trials. Since the Fe_3O_4 particles studied in this work are not fully superparamagnetic, its hybrid nanosystem may not be ideal for application in magnetic resonance imaging. Reducing the size of the Fe_3O_4 particles would help resolve this issue.

We have also measured the AC hysteresis loops for these samples using a home-made device, as commented before. As it can be observed in Fig. 2d, for fields lower than $H_{AC} \sim 200$ Oe, the hysteresis loops have the typical aspect of minor loops (Rayleigh lancets), with a very narrow shape, low coercivity (H_C) and remanence (M_r) and, therefore, small area and heating efficiency. However, as the applied field increases, both H_C and M_r start to increase. These results can be qualitatively understood considering recent works by, among others, Mamiya *et al.*⁵⁸ and Usov *et al.*⁵⁹ According to these calculations, for low field values the power absorption is mainly caused by viscous losses in the system, and this regime is characterized by a sharp decrease in the hysteresis loop area. However, when the applied AC field overcomes the effective anisotropy of the system, the hysteresis losses dominate, maximum heat power is transferred to the MNPs and the area of the hysteresis loops appreciably increases. Although the fields we can apply are not high enough to obtain major hysteresis loops (which give the best heating efficiency), these results clearly reveal that in order to get the best magnetic hyperthermia response out of our MNP, AC fields $H_{AC} > 200$ Oe need to be applied.

Magnetic hyperthermia and photo-thermal therapy

We carried out magnetic hyperthermia experiments both in water and agar (2 wt.% in water). The particles were measured in agar to restrict the physical motion of the particles which contributes to the heating, and separate this way both the hysteresis losses and Brownian motion contributions. The 2% agar solution also is used to mimic higher cancer cells viscosity. Agar phantoms have long been used in magnetic hyperthermia studies.⁶⁰ Our results prove that the major contribution to the heating efficiency of the studied nanoflowers comes from magnetic hysteresis losses rather than Brownian motion contribution (Figure S6 in the supplementary information). During the magnetic hyperthermia experiments, we measured the heating curves for different values of the external AC applied magnetic field, H_{AC} , (Fig. 3a). The heating rate reduces significantly with decreasing magnetic field and, therefore, the final reached temperature is lower. As a result, it seems that a magnetic field $H_{AC} > 600$ Oe is needed to reach the therapeutic temperature window (40 – 44° C), where cancer cells can be damaged while preserving healthy ones.¹⁸ The heating efficiency of the nanoflowers, expressed in terms of the SAR magnitude, can be estimated from the initial slope of the T vs. time curves ($\Delta T/\Delta t$):

$$SAR = \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t} \frac{C_p}{\varphi},$$

where C_p is the heat capacity of the liquid solvent (4.186 J/g K for water) and $\varphi = 2 \times 10^{-3}$ is the mass of Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers per unit mass of liquid. It can be noticed in Fig. 3b that the obtained SAR values are nearly zero with a flat response below $H_{AC} \sim 200$ Oe. This agrees with our previous observation of the AC hysteresis loop area being very small for fields below 200 Oe. Above this threshold value of the magnetic field, the SAR increases almost linearly from 24 to 167 W/g in the range $300 < H_{AC} < 800$ Oe. Therefore, two SAR regimes are distinguished and can be explained taking into account the morphology of the Fe₃O₄ MNPs, which are responsible for the magnetic hyperthermia response of the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers. When MNPs form aggregates due to strong dipolar interactions, the orientation of the magnetic moments along the direction of the oscillating external field is restricted. Then, heat loss processes do not start to occur until the applied AC magnetic field intensity is high enough to overcome the effect of the dipolar interactions.²² A maximum value of SAR ~ 160 W/g is reached for $H_{AC} = 800$ Oe. These results compare well with those reported in the literature for iron oxide MNPs of similar size.^{61,62} In order to understand the effects of Ag (core) size and Fe₃O₄ (shell) thickness on the heating efficiency of Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers, magnetic hyperthermia experiments were also performed on 210 nm Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers with 70 nm Ag core. The SAR values of the 210 nm Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers were found to be larger than those of the 120 nm Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers with 45 nm Ag core (see Supplementary Information Fig. S-7). This shows the possibility of tuning the heating efficiency of Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers by varying Ag (core) size and/or Fe₃O₄ (shell) thickness. Upon increase in the Ag size, the absorption peak was also found to shift towards a higher wavelength, which is more desirable for practical applications.⁵¹ A thorough understanding of the effects of varying Ag (core) size and Fe₃O₄ (shell) thickness on the magnetic hyperthermia and photothermal properties of Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers is essential which will be a subject for our further systematic study.

Fig. 3c shows the photo-thermal response of the Ag cores for different laser power densities. We see a significant power-dependent behavior for the final attained temperature after 5 min of irradiation. A power density of $P = 0.93$ W/cm² is needed to reach temperatures above 40° C; however, the final temperature reached temperature climbs to 52° C when P is augmented to 1.60 W/cm². The evolution of the SAR as a function of the power density (Fig. 3d) displays a fast increase achieving a value of 185 W/g for $P = 1.60$ W/cm². Our results are similar to those reported for other noble metal nanoparticles.³¹

In order to reach a target temperature window of 40 – 44° C by using separately either magnetic hyperthermia or photo-thermal therapy techniques, values as large as $H_{AC} = 600$ Oe and $P = 0.93$ W/cm² are required, respectively. However, one major limitation in clinical trials is that the dose of magnetic field and laser irradiation exposures must be kept below safety limits with the aim to minimize the damage to healthy biological tissue while selectively killing targeted cancer cells. The maximum permissible exposure of skin to laser irradiation is established by the American National Standard for Safe Use of Lasers (ANSI) and varies as a function of the laser wavelength.³² In the case of magnetic hyperthermia, the Atkinson-Brezovich criterion¹⁹ establishes a limit for the maximum values of the AC applied magnetic field and the frequency so that the induced eddy currents in the body are kept small. However, simultaneous application of magnetic hyperthermia and photo-thermal therapy reduces substantially the required values for H_{AC} and P to heat within the target temperature window.

Let us focus now on the heating efficiency of our Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers under combined magnetic field and laser exposures. Figures 4a and 4b represent the heating curves of the nanoflowers during irradiation with constant laser power densities of 0.53 W/cm² and 0.93 W/cm², respectively, under different values of the applied magnetic field intensities. Comparing these curves with those obtained without laser irradiation, we can observe that the final reached temperatures are greatly enhanced. For example, for $H_{AC} = 400$ Oe, the attained temperature after 5 min of exposure changes from

30.8° C for $P = 0$ to 41.1° C and 48° C, for 0.53 and 0.93 W/cm², respectively. It is worth noting that for reaching a target temperature of 40 °C a magnetic field of 600 Oe is required in absence of laser irradiation. But this value decreases by a factor of three (200 Oe) when a laser power density of 0.93 W/cm² is simultaneously applied (Fig. 4c). This effect is even more noticeable in Fig. 4d, where the SAR values for different combinations of magnetic field magnitudes and laser power densities are displayed. For all magnetic fields, the SAR values increase drastically when a laser is applied simultaneously. As a result, the heating ability at $H_{AC} = 200$ Oe at $P = 0$ increases by more than one order of magnitude (from around 10 W/g to 130 W/g) for $P = 0.93$ W/cm². The TEM image of the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers after being exposed to the AC magnetic field (800 Oe) and laser (0.93 W/cm²) showed no change in morphology (Figure S8 in the supplementary information) which is of practical importance. In addition, we observe that in the low-field region, not only the SAR of the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers is relatively small, but also that of individual Fe₃O₄ NPs (Figure S9 in the supplementary information). Therefore, the combined use of magnetic field and laser exposure is even more promising in this H_{AC} - range, as it is more suitable for clinic trials and the laser-induced SAR improved is sharper. The above findings support the idea that designing new hybrid nanostructures with synergic plasmonic and magnetic properties for simultaneous photo-thermal therapy and AC magnetic hyperthermia hold the key for a new class of efficient nanostructured hyperthermia agents. For the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanosystem under our study, we note that individually both Ag and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are biocompatible but the cytotoxicity of this system remains to be examined. Further in vitro or in vivo studies of the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are therefore needed to fully realize their biomedical applications.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the heating efficiency of Ag(core)/Fe₃O₄(shell) nanoflowers has been greatly enhanced by combining the magnetic hyperthermia properties of magnetite with the photo-thermal response of silver. The SAR of the nanoflowers under low magnetic field (200 Oe) increases by an order of magnitude with simultaneous laser irradiation. Moreover, it is possible to obtain the same SAR value by using lower magnetic fields and laser power densities than required if only one technique were used. This study paves the way for designing more efficient photo-thermal and magnetic hyperthermia agents that minimize the damage to biological healthy tissue while selectively killing targeted cancer cells.

Supporting Information:

Size distribution X-ray diffraction (XRD), Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX): element-specific mapping, Size distributions for the core and shell crystallites, Ultraviolet – visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis), TEM image of the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers after exposing to the AC magnetic field (800 Oe) and laser (0.93 W/cm²) for the nanoflowers, Comparative SAR values of 120 nm Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers (2 mg/mL) dispersed in water and agar 120 and 210 nm Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers in water (2 mg/mL), Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers and individual Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are presented.

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Figure 1. (a) TEM micrograph of the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers. (b) SAED pattern corresponding to (a). (c) Superposition of the EDX elemental maps for Fe (green) and Ag (red). (d) Element-specific line profiles for Fe (green), O (blue) and Ag (red) recorded along the yellow line that passes through the nanoflower. (e) HRTEM image of an individual Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflower. (f) Detail of the central region of (e), showing the core/shell interface. (g) Fe₃O₄ shell crystallites.

Figure 2. (a) $M(T)$ curves in ZFC and FC conditions measured under a DC applied magnetic field of 100 Oe; Verwey transition is highlighted. (b) Room-temperature DC hysteresis loop. (c) Enlarged view of the central region of (b). (d) AC hysteresis loops for different values of the maximum H_{AC} field, $f = 300$ Hz and $T = 300$ K.

Figure 3. (a-b) Magnetic hyperthermia (a) Temperature elevation profile for the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers under different AC magnetic fields ($100 < H_{AC} < 800$ Oe) at a constant frequency, $f = 310$ Hz. (b) SAR vs. magnetic field curves obtained from (a). (c-d) Photo-thermal therapy (c) Heating curves under irradiation with a 442 nm laser for values of the power density ranging from 0.13 to 1.60 W/cm². (d) SAR vs. laser power density curves obtained from (d). All the measurements were performed for a 2 mg/ml concentration in agar (see text for details).

Figure 4. Magnetic hyperthermia and photo-thermal therapy. (a-b) Heating curves for the Ag/Fe₃O₄ nanoflowers under different AC magnetic fields ($100 < H_{AC} < 800$ Oe) at a constant frequency, $f = 310$ Hz, under irradiation with a 442 nm laser for two different power densities: 0.53 (a) and 0.93 (b) W/cm². (c,d) Temperature reached after 300 s of heating (c) and SAR (d) as a function of H_{AC} for different laser power densities. The blue zone in (c) evidences the therapeutic temperature window of 40 – 44° C.